

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
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Sacramento, California 95814-4700

In reply refer to:
2022-0007925-S7-001

December 1, 2022

Frances Malamud-Roam
Project Manager, Regulatory Division
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
San Francisco District
450 Golden Gate Avenue
San Francisco, California 94102-3406

Subject: Formal Section 7 Consultation on the West Bay Sanitary District Flow Equalization and Resource Recovery Facility Levee Improvements Project, City of Menlo Park, San Mateo County, California (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers File Number: 2018-00371S)

Dear Ms. Malamud-Roam:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps') February 14, 2022, letter requesting initiation of informal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) for the West Bay Sanitary District (WBSD, applicant) Flow Equalization and Resource Recovery Facility (FERRF) Levee Improvements Project (proposed project) in the City of Menlo Park, San Mateo County, California. At issue are the proposed project's effects to the federally endangered California least tern (*Sterna antillarum browni*), endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*)¹ and the threatened western snowy plover (*Charadrius nivosus nivosus*). On May 23, 2022, the Corps revised their determinations on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse and requested formal consultation for those species. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR § 402).

On July 5, 2022, the U.S. District Court of the Northern District Court of California vacated the 2019 regulations implementing section 7 of the Act. On September 21, 2022, the Ninth Circuit

¹ Until the Service officially adopts recent nomenclature changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union to Ridgway's Rail (*Rallus obsoletus*), we maintain the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) in this correspondence. Note, the change in taxonomic assignment does not change the listing status of the species.

Court of Appeals granted a request to stay the U.S. District Court of Northern California's July 5, 2022, order that vacated the 2019 Act regulations. On November 14, 2022, the U.S. District Court of Northern California granted a motion for remand without vacatur for the 2019 Act regulations. As a result, the 2019 regulations are again in effect, and the Service has relied upon the 2019 regulations in rendering this biological opinion. However, because the outcome of the legal challenges to 2019 Act Regulations is still unknown, we considered whether our substantive analyses and conclusions in this consultation would have been different if the pre-2019 regulations were applied. Our analysis included the prior definition of "effects of the action," among other prior terms and provisions. We considered all the "direct and indirect effects" and the "interrelated and interdependent activities" when determining the "effects of the action." As a result, we determined the substantive analysis and conclusions would have been the same, irrespective of which regulations applied.

On July 5, 2022, the U.S. District Court of the Northern District Court of California vacated the 2019 regulations implementing section 7 of the Act. On September 21, 2022, the Ninth Circuit Court of Appeals granted a request to stay the U.S. District Court of Northern California's July 5, 2022, order that vacated the 2019 Act regulations. On November 14, 2022, the U.S. District Court of Northern California granted a motion for remand without vacatur for the 2019 Act regulations. As a result, the 2019 regulations are again in effect, and the Service has relied upon the 2019 regulations in issuing our written concurrence on the action agency's "may affect, not-likely-to-adversely-affect" determination. However, because the outcome of the legal challenges to the 2019 Act regulations is still unknown, we considered whether our substantive analyses and conclusions would have been different if the pre-2019 regulations were applied in this informal consultation. Our analysis included the prior definition of "effects of the action." We considered all the "direct and indirect effects" and the "interrelated and interdependent activities" when determining the "effects of the action." We then considered whether any "effects of the action" that overlap with applicable ranges of listed species would be wholly beneficial, insignificant, or discountable to the species. As a result, we determined the substantive analysis and conclusions would have been the same, irrespective of which regulations applied.

The Federal action on which we are consulting is the Corps' issuance of a permit under Section 404 of the Clean Water Act of 1972, as amended, 33 U.S.C. § 1344 *et seq.*, and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899, as amended, 33 U.S.C. § 403 *et seq.*, to place fill in jurisdictional waters of the U.S. in San Francisco Bay. The Biological Assessment included a summary of the Bayfront Recycled Water Facility and the Treated Reverse Osmosis Effluent elements of December 2020 WBSD FERRF Draft Environmental Impact Report (DEIR). These elements are not part of the Federal action under consultation and will not be discussed further.

In considering your request, we have based our evaluation on the following: (1) the Corps' February 14, 2022, informal consultation initiation request letter; (2) the October 2021, Biological Assessment; (3) the August 4, 2022, technical memorandum regarding revisions to the October 2021, Biological Assessment; (4) the August 2022, Adaptive Management and Monitoring Plan; (5) the August 2022, Compensatory Mitigation Plan; (6) the December 2020, DEIR and the May 2021 Final Environmental Impact Report; (7) numerous emails and meetings resulting in project description changes and revisions; and (8) other information available to the Service.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the California least tern. The project footprint and Action Area do not provide breeding habitat but do provide foraging habitat. Disturbance from construction activity may temporarily deter terns from foraging near the Action Area but is not anticipated to result in adverse effects given the availability of foraging habitat within Westpoint Slough outside of the Action Area. It is unknown if the oyster reef or living shoreline will alter foraging habitat such that it would deter future foraging use in the Action Area.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the western snowy plover. The project footprint does not provide breeding habitat but does provide foraging habitat. Western snowy plovers nest in the Service's San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge Complex (Refuge) Ravenswood ponds adjacent to Bedwell Bayfront Park and within the range of noise disturbance from pile driving. Foraging plovers have been documented in Bedwell Bayfront Park along Flood Slough as cited in the Biological Assessment and may forage along Westpoint Slough. Bedwell Bayfront Park is frequented by the public and any plovers foraging nearby are subjected to disturbance from various types of recreational use in and around the park. Additionally, the pile driving, the loudest source of construction noise, will occur mostly outside of the March through September breeding season. Disturbance and noise from construction activity may temporarily deter plovers from foraging near the project footprint but is not anticipated to result in adverse effects given the availability of foraging habitat in Bedwell Bayfront Park, the Ravenswood ponds, and Cargill salt ponds near the Action Area.

The remainder of this document is the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

Consultation History

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| February 14, 2022 | The Service received the Corps' informal consultation initiation request letter and the October 2021, Biological Assessment via email. |
| March 7, 2022 | The Service emailed the Corps concurrence with the Corps' determinations for the California least tern and the western snowy plover but communicated that the Service could not concur with the determinations for the California clapper and salt marsh harvest mouse based on habitat loss and disturbance and requested quantification of loss of habitat. The Corps and Service exchanged subsequent emails regarding logistics of information exchanges. |
| March 29, 2022 | The Service attended a multi-agency meeting hosted by the Corps to discuss the project. |
| May 23, 2022 | The Corps revised the determinations for California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse from not likely to adversely affect to likely to adversely affect and requested formal consultation for those species. The |

Service responded acknowledgement and asked if the Corps expected project modifications.

May 24, 2022 The Corps emailed the Service with information that the applicant was working on design modifications.

June 1-2, 2022 The Corps emailed the Service that the applicant proposed a design alternative and to request meeting availability. The Service responded on June 2, 2022.

July 11-12, 2022 The Corps emailed the Service a summary of the June meeting that the Service was unable to attend and provided revised project documents. The Service and Corps exchanged emails regarding timing review and issuance of the consultation.

August 30, 2022 The Corps and Refuge exchanged emails regarding document transmittal.

September 2, 2022 The Corps and Service exchanged emails regarding status of review of the revised documents and consultation timing.

September 6, 2022 The Service's San Francisco Bay-Delta Office and the Refuge exchanged emails regarding project design, impacts, and comments.

September 15, 2022 The Corps and Service exchanged emails with the Service requesting additional information.

September 16, 2022 The Service received informational responses from Corps.

September 22, 2022 The Corps and Service exchanged emails.

September 23, 2022 The Corps, Service, and applicant's consultant exchanged emails.

September 27, 2022 The Corps, Service, and applicant's consultant exchanged emails. The Service's San Francisco Bay-Delta Office also emailed the Refuge regarding their review.

September 30, 2022 The Service received a project map from the Corps.

Early October 2022 The Corps and Service exchanged emails regarding public comments and meeting logistics.

October 6, 2022 The Refuge sent an email to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Office with their comments on the revised project documents.

October 11, 2022 The Service's San Francisco Bay-Delta Office responded to the Refuge.

- October 19, 2022 The Service attended a multi-agency meeting hosted by the Corps to discuss the project and public comments. The agencies were copied on the Corps' email to the applicant's consultant summarizing the meeting.
- October 20, 2022 The agencies were copied on the email exchange between the Corps' and applicant's consultant.
- October 21, 2022 The Corps and Service exchange emails regarding project questions and responses.
- October 24, 2022 The Corps and Service exchange emails regarding project questions and responses and consultation timing.
- October 25, 2022 The Corps, Service, and applicant's consultant exchange emails regarding language consistency in the documents.
- November 3-10, 2022 The Corps, Service, and applicant's consultant exchange emails regarding project information.
- November 10, 2022 A meeting between the Corps, Service, and the applicant's consultation was held to discuss project timing and sequencing and the proposed conservation measures.
- November 12, 2022 The applicant's consultant followed up the November 10th meeting with an email.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The proposed project purposes are to obtain Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) certification for the WBSD levee system and to protect the flow equalization capacity provided by WBSD's existing facilities at the FERRF site (including open air basins containing approximately 23.6 million gallons of sewage) from being lost to inundation under both current conditions and future sea level rise within the San Francisco Bay. The FERRF site is located at the end of Marsh Road in Menlo Park, adjacent to Bedwell Bayfront Park, on the edge of Flood Slough in the San Francisco Baylands. WBSD is not proposing changes to FERRF operations in this consultation.

Below is the Service's summary of the proposed project description based portions of the Biological Assessment and revisions iterated in emails and revised documents. As mentioned above, the Biological Assessment included actions that are not part of this consultation but are part of the DEIR. Some of the sections in the Biological Assessment combined information for both sets of actions and the Service has attempted to capture relevant information. Changes to the project description and design may require reinitiation of consultation.

Levee Sheet Pile Installation

Permanent sheet pile walls are proposed so that the engineered levees surrounding the FERRF site can be FEMA certified. Sheet pile walls are interlocking steel metal plates (anticipated to be 3/8-inch thick, 12-inch wide, 35 feet tall/long) that will be driven or vibrated into the existing earthen levees. The proposed thickness of the piles is based on predicted erosion rates and the minimum service life of the material. Approximately 3,700 linear feet of sheet piles would be placed at the top of the bank along the western and northern portions of the FERRF site, with a short, approximately 200-foot section extending onto Menlo Park land at the site entrance. A double wall (two walls in parallel) is planned on the north side of the site to improve seismic stability of the existing northern levee.

The sheet piles would be driven or vibrated into the ground approximately 30 feet deep. The sheet piles on the west side will be at an elevation 15 feet North American Vertical Datum of 1988 (NAVD 88). This height was selected to account for the FEMA flood height as well as the projected 50-year sea level rise height.

Early conversations with the sheet pile contractor indicated that a potential method to install the sheet piles could be the use of a single directional drill rig with a vibrational hammer. A key step in this process is to predrill through existing fill with an auger to make installation easier and reduce vibration. Spoils would not need to be extracted since the goal is just to break up the compacted levee soil for easier installation of the sheet piles.

Creation of Ecotone Slope/Living Shoreline

WBSD proposes to create an ecotone slope along a portion of the San Francisco Bay shoreline adjacent to the Menlo Park FERFF site. The living shoreline would be built by first installing temporary cofferdams at low tide to isolate the area from tidal action. The temporary cofferdams are expected to be sheet piles that would be vibrated into bay mud using a vibratory hammer (or similar machinery) staged at the top of the existing levee. Dewatering is not expected during cofferdam installation since it will be installed during low tide when water is not expected to be present. However, it may be necessary to remove groundwater intrusion and/or rainwater during construction.

Once the construction area is isolated from tidal action, the existing marsh vegetation would be mechanically stripped from the area after preconstruction surveys for special-status species are completed. The vegetation would be preserved on-site, watered, and protected so it can be used to revegetate the ecotone slope.

Locally sourced, imported fill would be used to raise the existing engineered levee to an elevation of 15 feet NAVD88, and on-site stockpiles and/or excavated soil will be used to construct the ecotone slope. The bay mud and topsoil fill used would be from reuse of on-site excavations to support the proposed plantings. Construction activities would take place land side and no activities are planned by boat or barge.

Once grading is complete, the areas would be inspected for stability and prepared for planting, as

appropriate. Plants from salvaged marsh sod, seeds, and container plants would be installed as determined by a site planting plan. Temporary irrigation would be provided during the plant establishment period, as necessary.

Once all revegetation is installed and inspected by a restoration ecologist the temporary cofferdam would be removed to reopen the area to tidal action. An Adaptive Management and Monitoring Plan has been prepared to ensure the success of the ecotone slope.

Creation of Tidal Marsh Habitat in Uplands-Onsite Mitigation for Waters of the U.S. Impacts

The proposed project will include the creation of approximately 0.65 acre of salt marsh habitat within existing uplands adjacent to and east of the ecotone slope along the northern portion of the site. This marsh habitat is proposed to offset the permanent impacts associated with the development of the ecotone slope/living shoreline. The marsh would be constructed by over excavating by approximately 12 inches and filling the area with bay mud. Once excavation is complete, the areas would be inspected for stability and prepared for planting, as appropriate. Plants from salvaged marsh sod, seeds, and container plants would be installed as determined by a site planting plan. Temporary irrigation would be provided during the plant establishment period, as necessary. Once all revegetation is installed and inspected by a restoration ecologist, the temporary cofferdam would be removed to reopen the area to tidal action. An Adaptive Management and Monitoring Plan has been prepared to ensure the success of the ecotone slope.

Installation of Oyster Reef Structures

To develop natural shoreline protection that can reduce wave energy and potential shoreline erosion over time, oyster reef structures will be added around the northernmost point near the existing helipad as well as along Flood Slough near the entrance to the site. These elements are anticipated to be placed between elevations of 2 and 5 feet NAVD 88 and will provide approximately 1,116 linear feet and 0.35 acre of native oyster habitat. It is anticipated that these elements will be sized to fit within this total area using pre-fabricated "Oyster Catcher" reef products developed by Sand Bar Oyster Company. These structures are biodegradable, being constructed of a combination of locally sourced bay mud, Portland cement, and coir fabric. As they degrade slowly over time, they leave only oyster shells behind. These structures are lightweight and modular and are designed with an open reef framework that is slightly elevated off the ground surface with anchoring elements to increase the development of pre-seeded oysters on the structures. The final design of these oyster reef elements is to be determined with the final design plans for the proposed project.

On-Site Storm Water Improvements

The FERRF has an existing 30-inch pipe, located approximately 20 feet east of the old Menlo Park Wastewater Treatment Plant, that extends from the Wastewater Treatment Plant north to an outfall to Westpoint Slough. Since the plant is no longer operational, wastewater is no longer discharged. The proposed action includes capping of this line and rerouting any drainage collected in this line to the existing flow equalization basins.

Storm Ditch Improvements

There is an existing ditch in Bedwell Bayfront Park, along the south and eastern portion of the FERRF site, that conveys stormwater from Bedwell Bayfront Park and discharges it to Westpoint Slough. The ditch in Bedwell Bayfront Park will be cleared of vegetation and be redesigned to a 5-foot-wide trapezoidal swale.

The applicant proposes the following improvements to the storm drain system for the site:

- An 18-inch-minimum storm drain system along the south border of the FERRF site discharging into Pond 1.
- A 1-foot-wide trapezoidal swale along the eastern side of the dirt path within the FERRF site discharging into Pond 1.
- An 18-inch open pipe is proposed on the northeast corner of the site within the City of Menlo Park discharging into Flood Slough. The 18-inch storm drainage system will receive sheet flow from a portion of Bedwell Bayfront Park. The sheet flow will drain into the 5-foot trapezoidal swale that is along the FERRF and City of Menlo Park border. The sheet flow will travel through pervious soil and be self-treating prior to entering the 18-inch pipeline and ultimately into Flood Slough. The 18-inch storm drain system within the City of Menlo Park will be comprised of an open pipe discharging into Flood Slough with a closure to assist in preventing bay water from backflowing into the site.
- An 18-inch-minimum storm drain system along the eastern side of Marsh Road discharging into Flood Slough.
- A 1-foot-wide trapezoidal swale along the western side of Marsh Road discharging into the 18-inch minimum storm drain system listed above.

The proposed improvements will provide slope protection and adequate capacity to prevent flooding, erosion, and siltation.

Entrance Roadway Grading and Retaining Wall

The entrance to the FERRF site from Marsh Road within Bedwell Bayfront Park would be graded with imported fill to bring the entrance roadway and immediate surrounding areas, including a short segment of the Bay Trail, up to 15 feet NAVD88. Approximately 2,500 cubic yards of fill are anticipated. A short (less than 5 feet high) retaining wall is planned just inside the entrance at the southwest corner of the pond closest to the entrance. Existing paved portions of Marsh Road and the FERRF entrance roadway affected by the proposed project activities would be repaved (returned to original condition) and unpaved areas would remain unpaved.

Adaptive Management and Monitoring Plan

The August 2022 Adaptive Management and Monitoring Plan (AMMP) includes: (1) maintenance and monitoring; (2) implementation monitoring; and (3) compliance monitoring. Compliance monitoring includes vegetation monitoring and protocol surveys for salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails. Surveys are proposed to determine if the species is utilizing the created habitat on the ecotone slope. The AMMP did not articulate a specific protocol. The Service's protocol survey for presence/absence for California clapper rail was

published in 2015. The Service does not currently have a protocol presence/absence survey for the salt marsh harvest mouse. Management actions that may result in additional effects to listed species will require reinitiation of this consultation.

Schedule

The general proposed schedule is as follows:

1. On-site improvements on inland side of levee (e.g., grading at Marsh Road and Bay Trail, construction of retaining wall at entrance of site, and improvements to stormwater system): Anticipated year-round starting as soon as possible in 2023 and continuing through February 2025 until complete.
2. Grading and sheet pile wall installation on levees surrounding FERRF: Outside rail breeding season, September 1, 2023 to January 31, 2024 and September 1, 2024 to January 31, 2025.
3. Ecotone slope grading and habitat removal: Outside rail breeding season, September 1, 2023 to January 31, 2024.
4. Cofferdam installation: Outside rail breeding season, September 1, 2023 to January 31, 2024 and September 1, 2024 to January 31, 2025 (if needed for areas not already isolated such as marsh creation area or oyster reef area).
5. Ecotone slope revegetation and marsh habitat creation: Anticipated February 1, 2024 to January 31, 2025 until completed.
6. Cofferdam removal: Anticipated February 1, 2025 or sooner depending on completion of the ecotone slope.
7. Oyster reef installation: Outside rail breeding season, September 1, 2023 to January 31, 2024 or September 1, 2024 to January 31, 2025.
8. Adaptive Management Plan: Year-round February 1, 2025 through February 1, 2026.

Conservation Measures

The applicant proposes the following measures that have been adapted from the Final Environmental Impact Report (FEIR) and includes additional applicable measures to protect water quality. The Service has removed some FEIR-specific language that is not germane to this consultation and revised text per the November 10, 2022, meeting.

1. *BIO-1a: Biological Monitoring During Construction in the Marsh.* A Service-approved biological monitor will be present during all construction activities within the marsh or in vegetated areas within five (5) feet of the marsh to look for listed species that may be impacted by construction. For example, when construction personnel need to install the

ecotone slope cofferdam and/or exclusion fencing and remove vegetation, the biological monitor will first inspect the vegetation to determine whether any salt marsh harvest mice are present. If any animals are present, they will be allowed to leave the area on their own, or the location of the in-marsh work will be adjusted to ensure to minimize impacts to listed species. The biologist shall have stop-work authority if any listed species is detected in an area where it may be injured or killed by construction activities. In the event that listed species are found within or directly adjacent to the project site, a Service-approved biologist shall contact the Service for further guidance regarding the appropriate measures to implement.

The Service-approved biological monitor will document all monitoring activities in a monitoring report. The biological monitor will also ensure that BIO-2a through k are implemented as necessary to protect listed species.

2. *BIO-1b: Measures to Protect Water Quality.* During all construction in and near tidal aquatic habitat, standard Best Management Practices will be used to minimize erosion and impacts to water quality. These are reported in the FEIR and will be included in the Stormwater Pollution Prevention Plan prepared for the proposed project. Compliance measures that protect water quality help reduce potential impacts to biological resources.
3. *BIO-1c: Noise Minimization.* As a Best Management Practice to minimize noise impacts, the sheet piles shall be installed using a "soft-start" method by pausing after the first 15 seconds at a reduced energy twice before vibrating the sheet piles in at full capacity.
4. *BIO-2a: Worker Environmental Awareness Training.* A Service-approved biologist will prepare a worker environmental awareness fact sheet with: (1) the description and status of the species; (2) the habitat of the species; (3) the legal ramifications of impacting the species; (4) a list of measures being taken to reduce impacts on these species during project construction (including preconstruction surveys, minimizing trash that attracts predators, and other measures); and (5) what to do if the species are encountered. All construction personnel working on the site will participate in a worker environmental awareness training conducted by the Service-approved biologist and will sign an acknowledgment that they have participated in the worker environmental awareness training.
5. *BIO-2b: No Pets.* No pets (e.g., dogs or cats) will be brought to the project site to avoid harassment, killing, or injuring of wildlife.
6. *BIO-2c: Food Trash Removal.* To minimize attraction of predators such as racoons and feral cats all workers will be required to secure their food related trash and remove it daily. The site foreman shall assure that all food trash related to the construction work is secured and removed.
7. *BIO-2d: Minimize Non-daylight Work; Prepare Lighting Plan.* Some nigh-time work may occur. Project lighting during construction activities shall be limited in consideration of the potential impacts to listed species. If early morning, early evening, or night lighting

is necessary during construction, a lighting plan shall be prepared in consultation with a Service-approved biologist.

8. *BIO-2e: Work During Extreme High Tides.* To avoid the loss of individual salt marsh harvest mice that may shelter in the work area during extreme high tides, a Service-approved biological monitor shall be present when work around the perimeter of the FERRF site occurs during extreme high tides, such as King Tides. The Service-approved biological monitor shall complete a pre-construction survey prior to construction activities in these areas. The biologist shall have stop-work authority if any listed species are detected in an area where it may be injured or killed by construction activities. Areas within the cofferdam or wildlife exclusion fence are expected to exclude mice and would not require a pre-construction survey. In the event that listed species are found within the project site, a Service-approved biologist shall contact the Service for further guidance regarding the appropriate measures to implement. Also see measure BIO-3 for California clapper rail measures at extreme high tide.
9. *BIO-2f: Limit Vegetation Removal.* To minimize the loss of individual harvest mice from any excavation, fill, or construction activities in suitable habitat, vegetation removal will be limited to the minimum amount necessary to complete the project.
10. *BIO-2g: Vegetation Removal Methods.* Vegetation removal will occur under the supervision of a Service-approved biologist as noted in BIO-2a. The vegetation shall be removed with hand tools (e.g., weed-eater, hoe, rake, trowel, shovel) on a progressive basis, such that it allows species to find adjacent cover. The biologist shall monitor the rate of vegetation removal to ensure that any harvest mice present are able to escape to cover that will not be impacted, and will specify whether vegetation needs to remain in a certain area temporarily to facilitate dispersal of mice into habitat outside of the impact area.
11. *BIO-2h: Exclusion Fence.* Following the hand-removal of vegetation, exclusion fencing will be erected around the outer boundary of the work area that is adjacent to harvest mouse habitat that is to remain intact to ensure that this species is excluded from the construction area. However, if the cofferdam for the proposed project excludes the species additional exclusion fencing is not necessary. The installation of the fence will be supervised by a Service-approved biologist. This fencing will consist of heavy plastic sheeting or metal material that cannot be climbed by harvest mice, buried at least 4 inches below the ground's surface, and with at least 1 foot (but no more than 4 feet) above the ground. All supports for the fencing will be placed on the inside of the work area. A 24-foot buffer will be maintained free of vegetation around the outside of the exclusion fencing. The fencing will be inspected daily during the project construction period, and any necessary repairs will be made within 24 hours of when they are found. If any breaks in the fencing are found, the biologist will inspect the work area for salt marsh harvest mice. If any individuals are found, all work that could impact these individuals will cease until the individuals have left the impact area on their own. If an injured or killed mouse is discovered at any time during project activities, all work shall cease immediately and the Service shall be contacted for further direction.

12. *BIO-2j: Prohibition of Plastic Monofilament Netting.* Monofilament plastic netting, including in temporary and permanent erosion control measures (such as straw wattles), shall not be used, regardless of whether the netting is biodegradable or not. Burlap or jute wrapped straw wattles are acceptable.
13. *BIO-2k: Monitoring and Adaptive Management Plan.* The proposed project shall include a plan to restore and monitor natural habitats impacted by the proposed project, particularly the ecotone slope area. At a minimum the plan shall be submitted in the permit package to the Corps required under Section 404 of the Clean Water Act and the permit package to the Regional Water Quality Control Board under Section 401 of the Clean Water Act for review.
14. *BIO-3:*
- To minimize impacts to individual rails, activities within or adjacent to habitat will not occur within two hours before or after extreme high tides (6.5 feet or above as measured at the Golden Gate Bridge), when the marsh is inundated, and rail movement may be altered. If the work area is protected by a cofferdam and/or wildlife exclusion fence and rails are not likely to be present within the buffer zone, the work can continue with a biological monitor present, but shall be halted if a rail is detected within the buffer zone.
 - If a California clapper rail nest or adult is encountered during any project-related activity, the observer(s) shall immediately move away from the nest/adult and the Service should be contacted to determine the appropriate course of action and/or mitigation measures.
15. *BIO-4a: Integrate Invasive Plant Management.* Prior to the start of construction activities, measures to control invasive plant species shall be specified and integrated with the Adaptive Management Plan for the ecotone slope restoration, with the purpose of protecting restoration areas from being significantly impacted by invasive weeds. Invasive plant removal in the salt marsh and on the adjacent levees shall be limited to hand tools as specified in BIO-2g and shall be removed before grading starts. If specified in the Adaptive Management Plan, invasive species management will extend into developed areas of the parcel as needed to protect the ecotone slope area.
16. *BIO-4b: Construction Measures to Minimize Invasive Plant Infestations.* The following measures shall be taken during construction to minimize invasive plant infestation and potential impacts of invasive plants on adjacent natural habitats, particularly the wetlands:
- All ground disturbing equipment used adjacent to native habitats will be washed (including wheels, tracks, and undercarriages) both before and after being used at the site. Worker personal gear, including boots, should also be cleaned and clear of plant material prior to entering the work area.

- All seeds and straw materials used on site shall be weed-free rice straw, and all gravel and fill material shall be certified weed free.
- The project will follow a Stormwater Pollution Prevention Plan as per the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System General Permit for Storm Water Discharges Associated with Construction and Land Disturbance Activities (Construction General Permit; Water Board Order No. 2009-0009-DWQ), to reduce stormwater runoff which can carry the seed of invasive plants to other locations.
- All disturbed soils within sensitive habitats and adjacent levee slopes will be stabilized and planted in accordance with the plan prepared for the proposed project.
- Soil and vegetation removed from weed-infested areas will not be used in general soil stockpiles and will not be redistributed as topsoil cover for the newly filled areas. All weed-infested soil will be disposed of off-site at a landfill or buried at least 2.5 feet below final grade.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” The Action Area for this consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the proposed project and the broader area that, while outside the proposed project footprint, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, dust, light, or changes in habitat associated with the proposed project. The Action Area consists of the project footprint that includes all work and staging areas within the FERRF and bayside of the levee, Flood Slough, Westpoint Slough and an extended area up to 3,200 feet from pile driving to account for noise effects to listed species. The Service estimates the Action Area, based on several information exchanges, to be approximately 910 acres. This area excludes the majority of Bedwell Bayfront Park.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably will be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the

factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the *Status of the Species*, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of Species

California Clapper Rail

Information about the California clapper rail biology and ecology is available in the Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the California clapper rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. Information about the salt marsh harvest mouse biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the salt marsh harvest mouse 5-year review at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3630.pdf (Service 2021). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The *Environmental Baseline* includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal Projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

Flow Equalization and Resource Recovery Facility

The proposed project is located at and adjacent to the WBSD's 20-acre Menlo Park FERRF site, at 1700 Marsh Road, adjacent to Bedwell Bayfront Park in Menlo Park, San Mateo County, California. The FERRF contains three wastewater detention ponds that provide a combined 23.5 million gallons of wastewater storage for WBSD flows when the conveyance system to the plant is at capacity, e.g., during wet weather events or when the conveyance system to the plant is undergoing maintenance or repairs. The FERRF site also contains the decommissioned Menlo Park Wastewater Treatment Plant (WTTP) that was in service from 1952-1980. WBSD currently also uses the FERRF site as extra office space and an auxiliary corporation yard for equipment and material storage, training exercises, pump repair workshop, and as a Capital Improvement Project staging area. In addition, WBSD provides space for Save the Bay to operate raised beds containing salt marsh plant propagation area.

The FERRF site generates noise from the use of pumps to fill and empty the equalization basins (during peak flow/maintenance periods only), access and use of the operations building by WBSD staff, and access and use of the small nursery operated by Save the Bay. The pumps used to fill and discharge the equalization basins are contained in a small building and do not operate continuously nor contribute substantially to the ambient noise environment near the FERRF. Access and use of the FERRF site by WBSD and nursery staff is not considered substantial noise generating activity. Actual ambient noise conditions were not included in the consultation documents.

The FERRF site is largely unpaved. The only impervious areas at the site are the remnant WTTP facilities and a portion of the entrance driveway into the site. Northern coastal salt marsh and tidal slough are located along the western and northern shorelines; and developed and annual grassland border the eastern and southern boundaries of the FERRF property. These are discussed in more detail below.

Wastewater Detention Ponds

There are three wastewater ponds located with the FERRF site that comprise approximately 11.33 acres. Two of the ponds are used for flow equalization and one pond is used for emergency storage of wastewater. The flow equalization ponds provide storage for combined stormwater and sewer wastewater flows during peak flow events or during conveyance system maintenance or repairs to prevent sanitary sewer overflows out of manholes until such times the flows can be routed to the regional Silicon Valley Clean Water Wastewater Treatment Plant in Redwood City. These ponds are mainly used during the rainy season, or for system maintenance and repair, and therefore are empty when not in use.

Because these ponds do not have a permanent pool of water, are hydrologically isolated from the Bay, and are devoid of vegetation, they do not provide breeding habitat for fish, amphibians, or reptiles. However, the ponds provide foraging habitat for avian species, including western snowy plover, that routinely forage in the adjacent salt marsh due to presence of algae and brine shrimp (Order Decapoda) when the ponds are in use. American avocet (*Recurvirostra*

americana) is known to forage in the ponds; and cliff swallow (*Petrochelidon pyrrhonota*) and barn swallow (*Hirundo rustica*) have been observed foraging over the ponds as cited in the Biological Assessment.

Developed Areas

Developed land cover is approximately 10.64 acres of the FERRF and includes areas with permanent structures, impervious surfaces, unpaved high-use areas, or areas regularly disturbed by human activities. Generally, these areas are devoid of substantial vegetation cover but may contain areas of ruderal and landscaped vegetation. Within the Action Area, developed land cover includes the levees, hardpack dirt roads, buildings, staging and storage areas, and the decommissioned water treatment facility (Appendix D, Photo 2). Within the developed land cover, there are scattered areas of ruderal (disturbed) vegetation, mostly along the levee roads and perimeter of the site and landscaped trees adjacent to the buildings. The developed habitat is frequently utilized by humans, and both paved and gravel portions of this habitat are well-maintained. Non-native species are strongly dominant, generally outcompeting other forb and native grass species that may otherwise be present. Herbaceous species observed included slender oat (*Avena barbata*), black mustard (*Brassica nigra*), fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*), bull mallow (*Malva nicaeensis*), wild radish (*Raphanus sativus*), red stemmed filaree (*Erodium cicutarium*), Jersey cudweed (*Pseudognaphalium luteoalbum*), fumitory (*Fumaria* sp.), and smilo grass (*Stipa miliacea* var. *miliacea*). Trees observed included Lollypop tree (*Myoporum laetum*), olive (*Olea europaea*), and Mexican fan palm (*Washingtonia robusta*).

California ground squirrels (*Spermophilus beecheyi*) occur on the levee slopes within and adjacent to the FERRF. Their burrows provide nesting habitat for western burrowing owl (*Athene cunicularia*). Also, many of the wildlife species that use the adjacent marsh habitat may move through the developed portions of the FERRF when traveling between more natural habitats. In addition, the levees are important to tidal marsh species during very high tides, such as king tides. During such events, most of the salt marsh habitat is inundated, and animals such as California clapper rails, California black rails (*Laterallus jamaicensis coturniculus*), and salt marsh harvest mice may take refuge in the vegetation along the slopes of the levees.

Nesting birds have been observed using the dilapidated structures of the decommissioned water treatment plant within the FERRF site and a cliff swallow colony was observed nesting under the eaves of the Fortistar Mitigation Group Building, which is adjacent to the project area along the southern boundary. In addition, a nesting pair of killdeers (*Charadrius vociferous*) have been observed in the dry area of a wastewater detention pond. Also, small fish are present in the aeration/clarifier tanks of the decommissioned wastewater treatment facility and a striped skink (*Mephitis mephitis*) was observed exiting from under the existing decommissioned building as cited in the Biological Assessment.

California Annual Grassland (Avena barbata Alliance – Wild Oats Grassland)

California annual grassland is an herbaceous plant community that is typically dominated by non-native annual grasses. This vegetation type is found in Bedwell Bayfront Park. The dominant grass observed was slender oats. Other grasses observed included foxtail barley

(*Hordeum murinum*) and Harding grass (*Phalaris aquatica*). Herbaceous species observed included fennel, purple salsify (*Tragopogon porrifolius*), rose clover (*Trifolium hirtum*), bristly ox tongue (*Helminthotheca echioides*), and smilo grass. Small stands of trees were also observed in the grassland, including Australian pine (*Casuarina equisetifolia*) and blue gum (*Eucalyptus globulus*).

California ground squirrels occur in the grassland areas. Other rodent species that occur in the grassland habitat in the Action Area include the California vole, Botta's pocket gopher (*Thomomys bottae*), and deer mouse (*Peromyscus maniculatus*). Diurnal raptors such as redtailed hawks (*Buteo jamaicensis*) forage for these small mammals in grasslands during the day, and at night nocturnal raptors, such as barn owls (*Tyto alba*), will forage for nocturnal rodents. Mammals such as the raccoon and striped skunk utilize the grassland habitat in the Action Area for foraging. Reptiles such as western fence lizards (*Sceloporus occidentalis*), western terrestrial garter snakes (*Thamnophis elegans*), and southern alligator lizards (*Elgaria multicarinata*) may occur in small numbers within the California annual grassland in the Action Area.

Northern Coastal Salt Marsh (Sarcocornia pacifica Alliance – Pickleweed Mats)

The northern coastal salt marsh habitat extends contiguously along the western and northern edges of the FERRF and the Action Area. This tidal salt marsh habitat is inundated with water, is subject to tidal ebbs and flows, and is heavily dominated by pickleweed with patches of California cordgrass (*Spartina foliosa*) growing in wetter areas. Along the upper margins of the salt marsh, saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*), marsh gumplant (*Grindelia stricta*), and alkali heath (*Frankenia salina*) are common.

Northern coastal salt marsh supports some of the rarest wildlife species in the San Francisco Bay. The California clapper rails nests in cordgrass, dense stands of pickleweed, and marsh gumplant in tidal marsh habitats in and around the Action Area. This species is found in the lower marsh zone where numerous small tidal channels are present. California black rails are also known to occur in northern coastal salt marsh as winter residents.

The salt marsh harvest mouse occurs in the upper zone of the salt marsh where pickleweed is the dominant plant. Alameda song sparrows (*Melospiza melodia pusillula*) and Bryant's savannah sparrows (*Passerculus sandwichensis alaudinus*) also nest in the salt marshes. Shorebirds, swallows, herons, egrets, blackbirds, and other avian species roost and forage, often in large numbers, in tidal salt marsh habitats in the Action Area, but most do not breed in these areas. Common species that forage in salt marsh habitat include the black-necked stilt (*Himantopus mexicanus*), American avocet, and willet (*Tringa semipalmata*).

Tidal Slough

Tidal slough habitat includes open water and mudflat portions of the Action Area, including open water in Flood and Westpoint sloughs and the smaller channels interspersed with the salt marsh along the northern edge of the Action Area. The open water habitat is devoid of vegetation with beds of viscous bay mud, and algal growth exposed at low tide. Because the open water

channels are interspersed throughout the northern coastal salt marsh, the animal species that occur in this habitat are similar to those described above for the salt marsh habitat.

At low tide, mudflats are exposed along the tidal sloughs. Mudflats are formed when mud is deposited by the tides and contain high densities of invertebrate animals such as insects, bivalves, crustaceans, and polychaete worms that are food for many bird species. A variety of shorebirds, including the western sandpiper (*Calidris mauri*), least sandpiper (*Calidris minutilla*), dunlin (*Calidris alpina*), willet, marbled godwit (*Limosa fedora*), short-billed dowitcher (*Limnodromus griseus*), and black-bellied plover (*Pluvialis squatarola*), forage on these mudflats when they are exposed. Such shorebirds are most abundant during fall and spring migration and during the winter non-breeding season.

Refuge Lands

The Action Area based on noise effects reaches to the Refuge's Greco Island South immediately north of the project footprint and the Ravenswood ponds immediately adjacent to Bedwell Bayfront Park to the east. Greco Island South contains extensive marsh salt marsh habitat. The Ravenswood ponds contain seasonally dry salt pannes and salt marsh habitat. Tidal marsh restoration is occurring within the Ravenswood pond complex as part of the South Bay Salt Pond Restoration Project. The Service issued a biological opinion for the South Bay Salt Pond Restoration Project Program and Phase 1 on August 12, 2008 (Service file number: 81420-08-F-0621) and the first part of Phase 2 on November 21, 2017 (Service file number: 08FBDT00-2017-F-0109-2)

California Clapper Rail

The FERRF is located immediately south of Greco Island South, part of the Service's Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge and east of Flood Slough. California clapper rails have been consistently detected at Greco Island South and Westpoint Slough/Flood Slough in the on-going surveys conducted for the Invasive Spartina Project (Olofson Environmental, Inc. 2018, 2020, 2021). Additionally, rails were heard calling from the salt marsh habitat within the Action Area during the various field surveys for the proposed project. High quality habitat occurs within and adjacent to the project footprint. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume California clapper rails utilize the salt marsh habitat within the proposed project area and that they may be subject to effects from construction in the adjacent marshes on Greco Island South and adjacent to Flood Slough.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

As discussed above, high quality salt marsh habitat is located along Flood and Westpoint Slough within the project footprint and larger Action Area. Salt marsh harvest mice were trapped in the salt marsh along Flood Slough in the late 1980s (California Natural Diversity Database Occurrence # 134 accessed via the Service's internal base map application) and are known to occur on Greco Island South and the Ravenswood ponds outside of the Action Area. Based on historical occurrences and the presence of high quality habitat, it is reasonable to assume salt marsh harvest mice utilize the salt marsh habitat within proposed project footprint and that they

may be subject to effects from construction in the adjacent marshes on Greco Island South and adjacent to Flood Slough.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it will not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the Action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Habitat

Construction of the ecotone slope/living shoreline will result in the permanent habitat loss to 0.11 acre (conversion of 0.06 acre of tidal slough/mudflat to tidal salt marsh and 0.05 acre of tidal salt marsh to uplands) and temporary loss of 1.43 acres. For the majority of the ecotone slope, marsh vegetation will be salvaged and placed back on the ecotone slope once the grading is complete. The placed marsh vegetation will remain rooted in the bay mud topsoil throughout the process. WBSD expects forage and cover functionality should be near pre-disturbance conditions within a few months of construction. According to the applicant, the ecotone slope, once fully constructed, is estimated to result in a total of approximately 1.54 acres of marsh habitat and approximately 0.73 acre of uplands along the northern levee of the FERFF. The project revisions from the applicant did not articulate how these estimations were calculated. The uplands are anticipated to transition to salt marsh habitat based on migration of the marsh habitat over time with sea level rise.

To minimize the effects from the conversion of salt marsh habitat to uplands, the project will create approximately 0.65 acre of new salt marsh habitat east of the proposed ecotone slope/living shoreline and in a narrow band of disturbed uplands and water detention basin between the levee and the high tide line. This area will be planted immediately and opened to tidal flow and will be monitored for success. There will likely be a temporal loss from the conversion of habitat to when the created marsh will be fully established. Preservation of these habitats in the form of a conservation easement or similar instrument was not proposed.

The intent is to provide a mosaic of habitats that are resilient to sea level rise and protect the FERFF. The applicant modeled existing conditions and future conditions with the proposed project in place. Based on this modeling, the project is not expected to impact adjacent tidal marsh habitat at Greco Island. However, the AMMP includes a requirement to conduct a visual assessment of adjacent habitats through photo documentation and observations from the site each year after construction. Any changes to habitat will be noted in the monitoring reports and necessary remedial actions will be coordinated with the regulatory agencies. Any physical impacts to habitat on Greco Island and subsequent remedial actions will require reinitiation this of consultation.

Noise

According to Barber *et al.* (2009), noise levels above 3 dBA above background levels can result

in a 50 percent reduced listening area and 30 percent reduced alerting distance in wildlife while noise levels above 10 dBA above background levels can result in 90 percent reduced alerting distance. The Transportation Noise Control Center (1997) found that noise levels over 80 dBA above background levels caused behavior disruption in foraging, breeding, egg incubation, and rearing of young in various bird species. In a study by Rasmussen *et al.* (2009), lab mice exposed to construction noise levels 70-90 dBA above background levels for ≥ 1 hour/day during gestation led to decreased reproductive efficiency (by decreasing live birth rates and increasing the number of stillborn pups).

Sheet Pile Wall Installation

This construction phase is anticipated to involve the use of a vibratory hammer/pile driver, as well as other typical equipment such as an auger drill rig, excavator, loader, and dozer. Based on noise studies, airborne sound from a single source (i.e., a “point” source) radiates uniformly outward in a spherical pattern as it travels away from the source. The sound level attenuates at a rate of 6 A-weighted decibels (dBA) for each doubling of distance. For example, the airborne source noise level from pile driving using an impact pile hammer (the noisiest equipment for the sheet pile installation) was assumed to be 101 dBA L_{max} (Maximum Sound Level, the highest sound level measured during a single noise event) based on the published noise emission level for impact pile driving at a distance of 50 feet (U.S. Department of Transportation 2006). The noise reduces 6 dBA for each doubling of distance; therefore, it would be 95 dBA at 100 feet, 89 at 200 feet, 83 dBA at 400 feet, 77 dBA at 800 feet, 71 dBA at 1,600 feet, 65 dBA at 3,200 feet, 59 dBA at 6,400 feet, and 53 dBA at 12,800 feet.

Neither the Biological Assessment or the DEIR provided ambient noise levels for the FERRF or the marsh but the DEIR provided the existing ambient noise level at Bedwell Bayfront Park as assumed to be in the range of 60 to 65 CNEL (Community Noise Equivalent Level) adjacent to the FERRF/Bedwell Park landfill gas flare, along Marsh Road (which provides park access and parking), and at the park entrance on Bayfront Expressway. The Service assumes ambient noise levels are lower in the tidal marsh areas north of the FERRF levee and on Greco Island South.

Sheet pile wall installation would occur around the northern and western perimeter of the FERRF and will impact rails and mice in habitat along Flood Slough, Westpoint Slough, and on Greco Island South.

Levee, Ecotone Levee, and Storm Drain Improvements

These activities would primarily occur along the northern (levee improvements) and eastern (storm drain improvements) perimeter of the FERRF site. This construction phase would also include the use of a vibratory hammer/pile driver to install the coffer dam, as well as typical equipment such as an excavator, loader, dozer, roller, and backhoe. Consistent with the analysis provided for the use of a vibratory hammer/pile driver during sheet pile wall installation, the use of a pile driver or vibratory hammer during levee, ecotone levee, and storm drain improvements could generate noise levels that greatly exceed ambient conditions onsite and into Greco Island South.

FERRF Entrance/Marsh Road Grade Improvements

This construction phase would include the use of typical equipment such as an excavator, loader, dozer, roller, and backhoe with the loudest piece of equipment being 85 dBA Lmax. Using the 6 dBA reduction for each doubling of distance; noise would be 79 dBA at 100 feet, 73 at 200 feet, 67 dBA at 400 feet, 61 dBA at 800 feet, and 55 dBA at 1,600 feet.

Effects to Individuals*California Clapper Rails*

In addition to temporary and permanent habitat loss, equipment noise, vibration, and increased human activity associated with project construction or monitoring may disturb California clapper rails by interfering with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, breeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Increased human activity and construction noise and vibrations may cause California clapper rails to flush from cover. As California clapper rails disperse away from the area, they may experience increased predation exposure from active movement, by seeking shelter in vegetation communities with less dense canopy cover, or failing to find available cover at all. As a result, displaced California clapper rails may also be subject to increased competition for resources in more densely occupied habitat. If construction occurs during the breeding season (February 1- August 31) disturbance to females during this time may cause nest abandonment and the loss of all eggs and chicks in the nest. The California clapper rail could experience reduced ability to vocalize with conspecifics, difficulty in maintaining or establishing territories, or experience reduced hours for sleeping and foraging. All of these behaviors can result in increased stress levels. Construction noise is likely to effect rails on Greco Island South. This area has been consistently recorded to have moderate to high relative densities and construction effects could result in instressed stressed, nest failure, increased predation and displacement. The applicant has proposed to conduct pile driving and habitat removal outside of the breeding season reducing, but not eliminating, construction effects during breeding season.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Similarly, adverse effects to salt marsh harvest mouse could occur from the use of heavy equipment, use of hand tools, noise, vibration, and increased human activity. If salt marsh harvest mice are present during construction and AMMP implementation, they will likely experience disruption in their normal behavioral patterns. They may respond to construction activities by relocating to refugial habitat within adjacent marsh to avoid noise and human interactions.

Vegetation removal may result in the removal of mouse nests and excavation of occupied habitat may cause mice to flee into adjacent habitat where predation could occur. Construction equipment could run over salt marsh harvest mice that move into the construction footprint. Walking through the emergent vegetation during construction clearance actions and post-construction maintenance and monitoring activities could result in salt marsh harvest mice being stepped on or crushed, resulting in injury or death.

Long-term consequences to salt marsh harvest mouse could result from post-construction management actions which do not control early infestations of invasive species like common reed and perennial pepperweed. Vegetation clearing will provide opportunities for the invasive species onsite and in adjacent waters to move into these newly disturbed areas. Common reed is known to create vast monocultures several meters tall and is not known to provide food resources to salt marsh harvest mice. Perennial pepperweed can create monocultures with limited cover, which provides poor upland refugia for salt marsh harvest mouse.

Although vegetation removal will reduce the potential for mortality from entombment or crushing during construction activities, salt marsh harvest mice will still be affected. Individual salt marsh harvest mice that move into adjacent upland habitat may be exposed to increased predation levels during more frequent active movement to forage or seeking shelter in vegetation communities with less dense canopy cover where there are predators present. Displaced salt marsh harvest mice may also be subject to increased competition for resources in a more densely-occupied habitat or habitat which contains sparser patches of suitable food. Disturbance to females from March to November could result in consequences such as nest abandonment or failure of the current litter. Therefore, displaced salt marsh harvest mice will likely suffer from increased predation, competition, and potentially reduced reproductive success overall.

General

Monitoring, maintenance and ongoing adaptive management could result in the same habitat and noise-related effects to California clapper rails and salt marsh harvest mice as could occur during initial construction, as discussed above. Surveys for the species as a component of the AMMP could result in harassment, capture, injury, and/or mortality.

Overall, the proposed project could result in local and temporary declines of California clapper rails and salt marsh harvest mice due to habitat conversion and to noise, vibrations, visual disturbance and crushing risk associated with construction, maintenance or ongoing management activities within or adjacent to tidal marsh habitat. However, these effects will be minimized with the implementation of the *Conservation Measures*. The successful restoration of habitat is intended to reduce the effect of habitat loss over time.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative Effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species* for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Action*, and the

Cumulative Effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the proposed project is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the *Environmental Baseline* and analyzed in consideration of all potential *Cumulative Effects*, will not rise to the level of reducing the likelihood of survival or recovery of the species based on the following: (1) the construction footprint is localized and physical effects to adjacent habitat on Greco Island South is not anticipated per the applicant's modeling; (2) the project will be phased to remove habitat outside of the California clapper rail breeding season; (3) proposed restoration of habitat temporarily removed and creation of new habitat from uplands; and (4) implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures* to minimize adverse effects.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harm in the definition of "take" in the Act means an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Such [an] act may include significant habitat modification or degradation where it actually kills or injures wildlife by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering (50 CFR 17.3) Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not the purpose of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the proposed protective measures and the terms and conditions of an incidental take statement and occurs as a result of the action as proposed.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the Applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions, or (2) fails to require the (Applicant) to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR § 402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse will be difficult to detect or quantify for the following reasons: their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through dense vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy of vegetation types resulting in low detectability. Therefore, the Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of harm, including injury or mortality from construction and monitoring disturbance and impairing the essential behaviors of all salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails within the approximate 910-acre Action Area. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of California clapper rails and

salt marsh harvest mice associated with the proposed project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that the level of anticipated take is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of California clapper rail or salt marsh harvest mouse.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse resulting from implementation of this Project have been incorporated into the proposed project's proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the incidental take of the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse:

1. All *Conservation Measures*, as described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* section of this biological opinion, shall be fully implemented and adhered to. Further, this reasonable and prudent measure shall be supplemented by the Term and Condition below. Please note, the *Conservation Measures* are different from the FEIR *Mitigation Measures*.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure compliance with the following term and condition, which implements the reasonable and prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. The Corps shall minimize the potential for harm, killing or other forms of take of the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse from proposed project-related activities by implementation of the *Conservation Measures* proposed in the *Description of the Proposed Action* in this biological opinion.
 - b. The Corps shall ensure the applicant provides final versions of the plans prior to project implementation for review and approval by the Service. The plans will contain updated designs and refer to *Conservation Measures* articulated in this biological opinion. If plans incorporate activities that were not expressly described and analyzed in this consultation, the Corps shall reinitiate consultation.
 - c. Plantings shall consist of native species only for all habitat types and include appropriate types for marsh habitat that don't facilitate predator perches.

- d. If mice nests are found within the construction area, work shall cease, and the Service shall be contacted immediately.
- e. Surveys for presence of California clapper rails as part of the AMMP shall use the Service's 2015 protocol for presence/absence and shall be provided to the Service for review and approval.
- f. Surveys for salt marsh harvest mice as part of the AMMP shall be provided to the Service for review and approval.
- g. The Corps shall ensure that the applicant immediately notifies the Service of any killed, injured, or entrapped California clapper rails or salt marsh harvest mice, within one (1) working day of the detection. Please contact the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-2664.
- h. The Corps and/or the applicant shall educate and inform personnel involved in the Project as to the *Conservation Measures* and Terms and Conditions in this biological opinion.
- i. The Corps shall comply with the reporting requirements of this biological opinion, including a post-construction report outlining how the *Conservation Measures* were implemented for this proposed project.
- j. The Corps and/or the applicant shall ensure any personnel identified as biological monitors or biologists, who are responsible for ensuring compliance with the *Conservation Measures* or other parts of the proposed project which may affect federally-listed species, be Service-approved prior to implementing those activities.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the proposed project is approached or exceeded, the Corps shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR § 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed Project. Injured listed species shall be cared by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed Project. Notification will be made to the contact above in Term and Condition 1b, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the *Salvage and Disposition of Individuals* section below.

2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and the California Natural Diversity Data Base ([https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/California Natural Diversity Database/Submitting-Data](https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/California%20Natural%20Diversity%20Database/Submitting-Data)).
3. The applicant shall submit a post-construction compliance report prepared by the on-site biologist to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within 60 calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the Project in meeting the avoidance and minimization measures; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known project effects on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take of these listed species, if any; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

1. Encourage or require applicants to minimize and/or avoid impacts to established high quality marsh habitat.
2. Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in restoration efforts.
3. Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.
4. Assist the Service with implementing other recovery actions identified within the most

current recovery plans for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the West Bay Sanitary District Flow Equalization and Resource Recovery Facility Levee Improvements Project. As provided in 50 CFR § 402.16,

(a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:

(1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;

(2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;

(3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or

(4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

(b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

(1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and

(2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager via email at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to the Service File Number: 2022-0007925-S7-001 in any future correspondence regarding this consultation.

Sincerely,

Donald Ratcliff
Field Supervisor

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